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**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2026, № 1 (Февраль)

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**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

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CLINICAL COURSE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH PRE-EXISTING CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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Abstract. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) remains a global health challenge, particularly in patients with pre-existing cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Accumulating evidence suggests that cardiovascular comorbidities significantly worsen the clinical course and prognosis of COVID-19. To evaluate the clinical features, complications, and outcomes of COVID-19 in patients with underlying cardiovascular diseases.

The presence of cardiovascular diseases is associated with a severe course and unfavorable outcomes of COVID-19. Early identification of high-risk patients and timely cardiovascular monitoring are essential to improve prognosis.

Keywords: COVID-19, cardiovascular diseases, clinical course, complications, prognosis.

КЛИНИЧЕСКОЕ ТЕЧЕНИЕ COVID-19 У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ПРЕДСУЩЕСТВУЮЩИМИ СЕРДЕЧНО-СОСУДИСТЫМИ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯМИ

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Аннотация. Коронавирусная инфекция 2019 года (COVID-19) остаётся одной из глобальных проблем здравоохранения, особенно у пациентов с предсуществующими сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями (ССЗ). Накопленные научные данные свидетельствуют о том, что наличие сердечно-сосудистых коморбидных состояний существенно утяжеляет клиническое течение и ухудшает прогноз COVID-19. Цель исследования оценить клинические особенности, частоту осложнений и исходы COVID-19 у пациентов с сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями.

Установлено, что наличие сердечно-сосудистой патологии ассоциируется с более тяжёлым течением и неблагоприятными исходами COVID-19. Ранняя идентификация пациентов группы высокого риска и своевременный кардиоваскулярный мониторинг имеют ключевое значение для улучшения прогноза.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, клиническое течение, осложнения, прогноз.

**ЮРАК-ҚОН ТОМИР КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИ МАВЖУД
БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРДА COVID-19 НИНГ КЛИНИК КЕЧИШИ**

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Аннотация. 2019 йилдаги коронавирус инфекцияси (COVID-19) жаҳон миқёсида соғлиқни сақлаш тизими учун долзарб муаммо бўлиб қолмоқда, айниқса юрак-қон томир касалликлари (ЮҚТК) мавжуд бўлган беморлар орасида. Илмий адабиётларда тўпланган маълумотлар юрак-қон томир касалликлари билан боғлиқ коморбид ҳолатлар COVID-19 нинг клиник кечишини сезиларли даражада оғирлаштириши ва касаллик прогнозига салбий таъсир кўрсатишини кўрсатмоқда. Тадқиқот мақсади юрак-қон томир касалликлари мавжуд бўлган беморларда COVID-19нинг клиник хусусиятлари, асоратлари ва натижаларини баҳолашдан иборат.

Юрак-қон томир касалликларининг мавжудлиги COVID-19 нинг оғир кечиши ва ноқулай клиник натижалар билан боғлиқ экани аниқланди. Юқори хавф гуруҳига кирувчи беморларни эрта аниқлаш ва ўз вақтида кардиоваскуляр мониторинг олиб бориш прогнозни яхшилашда муҳим аҳамиятга эга.

Калит сўзлар: COVID-19, юрак-қон томир касалликлари, клиник кечиш, асоратлар, прогноз.

Introduction. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), has

affected millions of people worldwide. Although the infection primarily targets the respiratory system, it has a pronounced systemic impact, particularly on the cardiovascular system. Patients with pre-existing cardiovascular diseases, including hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, and arrhythmias, represent a vulnerable population with an increased risk of severe disease and mortality.

Several mechanisms have been proposed to explain the interaction between COVID-19 and cardiovascular pathology, including endothelial dysfunction, cytokine storm, hypercoagulability, and direct myocardial injury mediated by angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors. Understanding the clinical course of COVID-19 in patients with cardiovascular comorbidities is crucial for optimizing management strategies and reducing adverse outcomes.

In recent years, COVID-19 coronavirus infection has emerged as a serious threat to public health on a global scale. It is described as a multi-organ pathological process that affects not only the respiratory system but also the cardiovascular, nervous, endocrine, and immune systems. The declaration of the COVID-19 pandemic by the World Health Organization on March 11, 2020, further highlighted the medical and social significance of this disease.

According to epidemiological data, the severe and complicated course of COVID-19 infection is often associated with advanced age and the presence of comorbid conditions, especially cardiovascular diseases. Cardiovascular pathologies such as arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, heart failure, arrhythmias, and atherosclerosis are characterized by

higher mortality rates and unfavorable clinical prognosis in patients with COVID-19.

The impact of the SARS-CoV-2 virus on the cardiovascular system is mediated through a number of pathogenetic mechanisms. The virus's entry into endothelial cells and cardiomyocytes via ACE2 receptors, systemic inflammatory response, "cytokine storm," hypercoagulable state, and microcirculation disturbances lead to myocardial damage and the development of thrombotic complications. This, in turn, increases the risk of severe COVID-19 and lethal outcomes.

Identifying comorbidities that promote multi-organ inflammatory processes in patients with COVID-19 worldwide, as well as the factors contributing to their development, and developing measures to counteract them are considered some of the most pressing medical and economic problems in modern infectiology.

At the same time, clinical practice shows that in patients with cardiovascular diseases, the effects of COVID-19 on the cardiovascular system persist not only during the acute phase but also in the convalescence period, with the maintenance of cardiovascular effects or the emergence of new forms. This situation necessitates long-term monitoring and comprehensive rehabilitation for these patients.

Materials and Methods. This retrospective observational study included 120 patients hospitalized with a confirmed diagnosis of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) during the period from 2020 to 2025. The study was conducted at the Bukhara State Medical Institute and its affiliated clinical hospitals. All patients were aged 18 years and older.

The diagnosis of COVID-19 was confirmed by detection of SARS-CoV-2 RNA using reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) from nasopharyngeal swab specimens. Patients were enrolled based on available medical records and completeness of clinical and laboratory data.

Depending on the presence of pre-existing cardiovascular diseases, patients were divided into two groups. The main group consisted of patients with documented cardiovascular diseases, including arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, chronic heart failure, and cardiac arrhythmias. The comparison group included patients without known cardiovascular pathology.

Data collection included demographic characteristics, clinical symptoms at admission, comorbid conditions, and vital signs. Laboratory investigations comprised complete blood count, inflammatory markers (C-reactive protein, ferritin), coagulation parameters (D-dimer), and markers of myocardial injury (cardiac troponin). Lung involvement was assessed using chest computed tomography (CT), and the severity of COVID-19 was classified according to current national and international clinical guidelines.

Clinical outcomes were analyzed, including the development of complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome, acute cardiac injury, arrhythmias, and thromboembolic events, as well as the need for intensive care unit admission, mechanical ventilation, and in-hospital mortality.

Statistical analysis was performed using standard statistical software. Continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation or median with interquartile range, while categorical variables were expressed as absolute numbers and percentages. Intergroup comparisons were carried out using appropriate parametric or non-parametric tests. A *p*-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results. A total of 120 patients with confirmed COVID-19 were included in the study. Based on the presence of pre-existing cardiovascular diseases, patients were divided into two groups: those with cardiovascular comorbidities and those without cardiovascular pathology.

Patients with cardiovascular diseases were predominantly older and more frequently presented with moderate to severe forms of COVID-19. The most common cardiovascular conditions observed in this group were arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, and chronic heart failure.

Clinical manifestations such as persistent fever, dyspnea, and decreased oxygen saturation at admission were more pronounced in patients with cardiovascular diseases. Radiological examination revealed more extensive lung involvement on chest CT in this group compared to patients without cardiovascular comorbidities.

Laboratory analysis demonstrated significantly higher levels of inflammatory markers, including C-reactive protein and ferritin, as well as coagulation indicators such as D-dimer, in patients with cardiovascular diseases. Markers of myocardial injury, particularly elevated cardiac troponin levels, were more frequently detected in this group, indicating a higher incidence of acute cardiac involvement.

Complications occurred more often among patients with pre-existing cardiovascular diseases. These included acute respiratory distress syndrome, acute cardiac injury, cardiac arrhythmias, and thromboembolic events. The need for intensive care unit admission and mechanical ventilation was also higher in patients with cardiovascular pathology.

In-hospital mortality was observed more frequently in the group of patients with cardiovascular diseases compared to those without such comorbidities, indicating a significantly poorer prognosis associated with underlying cardiovascular conditions.

Discussion. The results of this study demonstrate that the presence of pre-existing cardiovascular diseases significantly influences the clinical course and outcomes of COVID-19. Patients with cardiovascular comorbidities experienced a more severe disease course, higher rates of complications, and increased in-hospital mortality compared to patients without cardiovascular pathology. These findings are consistent with previously published data identifying cardiovascular diseases as a major risk factor for adverse COVID-19 outcomes.

Several pathophysiological mechanisms may explain the observed association between COVID-19 and cardiovascular diseases. SARS-CoV-2 enters host cells via angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptors, which are widely expressed in cardiac tissue and vascular endothelium. Viral-mediated endothelial dysfunction, combined with systemic inflammation and cytokine release, contributes to microvascular injury, thrombogenesis, and myocardial damage. In patients with pre-existing

cardiovascular conditions, these processes may exacerbate underlying pathology and lead to cardiac decompensation.

Elevated inflammatory markers and coagulation parameters observed in patients with cardiovascular diseases indicate a heightened inflammatory and prothrombotic state. This may explain the increased incidence of thromboembolic complications and acute cardiac injury in this group. Hypoxia due to severe pulmonary involvement further increases myocardial oxygen demand and may precipitate ischemic events and arrhythmias.

The higher frequency of intensive care unit admission and mechanical ventilation among patients with cardiovascular diseases reflects the severity of respiratory and systemic involvement. Moreover, increased mortality in this population underscores the importance of early identification of high-risk patients and close cardiovascular monitoring during hospitalization.

The findings of this study highlight the need for an integrated, multidisciplinary approach to the management of COVID-19 patients with cardiovascular comorbidities. Timely assessment of cardiac function, monitoring of biomarkers of myocardial injury, and appropriate anticoagulant and cardioprotective therapy may contribute to improved outcomes.

Despite its clinical relevance, this study has several limitations, including its retrospective design and single-center setting, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Future prospective, multicenter

studies with larger sample sizes are required to further elucidate the complex interaction between COVID-19 and cardiovascular diseases.

Conclusion. The findings of this study indicate that pre-existing cardiovascular diseases significantly worsen the clinical course and outcomes of COVID-19. Patients with cardiovascular comorbidities are more likely to develop severe forms of the disease, experience cardiovascular and thromboembolic complications, require intensive care, and have higher in-hospital mortality rates compared to patients without cardiovascular pathology.

Cardiovascular diseases should be considered an independent predictor of poor prognosis in patients with COVID-19. Early risk stratification, careful cardiovascular monitoring, and timely multidisciplinary management are essential to reduce complications and improve clinical outcomes in this high-risk population.

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